

Predicting ALSFRS-R thin-plate spline derived Progression Clusters using Initial Assessment Data

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Abstract. Assigning Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) cohorts with clinically homogeneous phenotypes is an essential requirement in both clinical trials for the modeling of drug effects, and also in establishing patient-specific treatment routes in clinical practice. While the study of progression clusters for ALS patients has gained interest in recent years, accurate identification of clusters and the subsequent effective leveraging of such clusters remains limited. In light of this, we have developed a method to predict patient trajectory cohort assignment based solely on clinical data at the first assessment. Our method learns trajectory groups based on longitudinal functional scores (ALSFRS-R) using unsupervised clustering based on thin-plate splines, and uses those clusters as targets for a subsequently trained supervised assignment model. We applied our method to the PRECISION-ALS Extant Dataset of over 21000 patients from sites across Europe. We identified a consistent set of 4 clusters from this dataset with a Silhouette Score of 0.66. A range of prediction methods were then applied to cluster prediction with an ensemble of multiple methods achieving an assignment F1 score of 0.65 on an externally validated dataset.

Keywords: Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis · ALS stratification · ALS progression

1 Introduction & Related Work

Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) presents a significant health challenge in the UK and worldwide, with its rapid, progressive nature leading to muscle wasting, and ultimately paralysis, with impacts on speech, swallowing, and breathing. The often unpredictable progression of ALS has spurred on significant research in the modelling of disease progression based around the Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis Functional Rating Scale (ALSFRS) and its revision ALSFRS-R. Accurate modelling of ALS progression aids time-to-event modelling for significant clinical events, e.g., survival, intervention times for NIV, gastrostomy. While parametric

and semiparametric models dedicated to ALS reached state of the art in modeling generalized trends of disease evolution based on multivariate data, they also revealed that group-specific approaches can increase prediction accuracy and clinical significance. Examining the distribution of clinical data within each group can reveal critical biomarkers that govern patient evolution [1]. As such the identification of cohorts based on ALSFRS trajectory measures, and the subsequent modelling of the relationship between such clusters and events as well as patient characteristics is of considerable interest.

A specific type of patient stratification is based on clustering time-dependent features that provide direct insight into disease evolution. Clustering trajectories with uneven time-steps, irregular behavior, and unequal lengths is in itself a challenging task. However, this task is complicated considerably by the fact that ALS is a rare disease and that patient data is typically gathered across multiple geographic sites and years, with the sometimes subjective nature of ALSFRS(-R) measurement leading to inconsistencies.

In terms of the state of the art, Ramamoorthy et al [2] have investigated probabilistic unsupervised methods such as Gaussian Process regression to cluster ALSFRS-R trajectories and Dirichlet Process Mixture Models to determine the number of clusters. This investigation, using the `MoGP` library, does not require specification of the number of clusters a priori, but it is computationally expensive and can find too many clusters, lowering clustering performance. More recently, Amaral et al [3] presented `Clustric` which considers 3-way data (patient, features, time) as ‘snapshots’ over the first 3 appointments which are subsequently clustered using the tool `TCtriCluster` [4] to learn ‘virtual patterns’, and subsequently calculates their 3D similarity matrix for hierarchical clustering, obtaining progression groups. For prediction of progression, the patient’s original cluster was predicted concretely for the next 3 appointments.

While both methods above, when applied to ALS data, have been found to show 4 clinically relevant groups, the latter has been shown to produce better clustering performance [3]. However, in both cases, group shifts are observed at inference times longer than 3 months, in part due to classification errors or insufficient input data (usually only 3 months are available for new patients). We argue that being able to identify meaningful progression clusters that are reliable, though not necessarily highly accurately assigned, can provide a valuable diagnostic tool if that assignment can be made solely on the basis of initial or very early assessment data. The study we present below aims to achieve this goal. We first present the data used, before methods and results.

2 Dataset

The work presented here was based on the multi-site European PRECISION-ALS Extant dataset [7], which contains ALS records of over 21000 patients as static and time-dependent clinical data and longitudinal data of functional ALSFRS-R scores, for over 6000 patients. The main clinical features available for all patients which also have longitudinal ALSFRS-R records (in total 6371 pa-

tients) are: (a) Continuous variables including ‘Total Score’, ‘Age at Diagnosis’, ‘Age at Onset’, ‘Diagnostic delay’, ‘ALSFRS-R early slope’; and (b) categorical variables including ‘Gender’, ‘Site of Onset’, ‘C9orf72 Status’, and ‘Bulbar onset’. We calculate the ‘ALSFRS-R early slope’ as the slope between the disease onset (assuming a maximum score of 48) and the first assessment. Data preprocessing involved one-hot encoding for categorical features, and standardization for continuous data. For testing we split the data using a 10-fold cross validation, while for external validation we applied a hold-one out strategy. For the modeling and results presented here, data from the Belvitge site was held back. This validation block contained data for 316 patient IDs.

3 Methods

Our analysis involves the initial identification of reliable patient cohorts based solely on ALSFRS progression trajectories, and the use of these clusters as labels for a supervised assignment process based solely on initial assessment measurements. Specifically, the following workflow indicates the steps of the method: (a) clean data (removing outlier trajectories); (b) cluster trajectories & assess group consistency by repeated clustering; (c) train classifiers using identified groups as labels; and (d) predicts ALSFRS-R trajectory groups for unseen patients.

Data quality is an important challenge as individual trajectory points that have sudden increases of more than 6 points (usually not easy to justify in the case of ALSFRS-R scores) or trajectories that have very large intervals between data points (larger than 5 years) decrease the quality of trajectory clusters (leading to points mistakenly assigned to other trajectory groups). For this reason, our method removes such trajectories from the clustering process.

The trajectory clustering algorithm uses k-means Expectation-Maximization (E-M), where means are defined by fitting a thin plate spline (TPS) to all points in a cluster. The E-M algorithm iterates between fitting a TPS on all points in a cluster (M) and reassigning points based on the nearest fit to the TPS (E). In this method, the trajectory emulates the shape of a thin metal plate under a warping force, modeled by the number of degrees of freedom (df). We found that using $df \leq n$ (the number of clusters) leads to mean trajectories with fewer maxima and inflection points. For this work, we used the R [5] implementation `Clustra` [6]. To evaluate cluster integrity, we use the information criteria (AIC, BIC) as well as the Silhouette score. While the TPS method does require a specification of the number of expected clusters n , it is common to evaluate for different values of n . After clustering, the dataset was then labeled with the hypothesized clusters. The resulting dataset contained 4587 IDs (individual patient data entries). We retrace the mean trajectory for each group using univariate spline interpolation to obtain a detailed view of the trendline. This provides us the prototypical behaviour for a given cohort progression, which in turn can inform clinical decisions.

The supervised prediction process to assign cohorts can make use of any multiclass machine learning or statistical method. For our work we have evalu-

Fig. 1. (a) Mean trajectories evaluated by **Clustra** with Silhouette scores and the AIC and BIC scores. (b) Mean trajectories retraced by univariate spline interpolation for each group. To increase resolution for interpolation purposes, the time axis is in [Days].

ated the performance using Random Forest, XGB, Linear Regression, AdaBoost, Support Vector Classifier, and Multilayer Perceptron; with the model presented here being based on a bagging ensemble across these methods.

4 Results

Experiments for various input parameters (random seeds, number of clusters n and degrees of freedom df to test the ‘replicability’ and clustering quality of trajectory groups (using the Silhouette, AIC and BIC scores) led us to identify 4 stable clusters with reliable Silhouette scores (above 0.6) and well-balanced number of members (Fig.1). The Silhouette scores for 4 clusters were better than those obtained for 5 or 6 clusters (below 0.56). The increasing part of the green trace in Fig.1(a) shows the presence of outliers (points belonging to other trajectory groups, misclassified due to their unusual characteristics). The collective distribution of points from all trajectories in each group is shown in Fig. 1(b) along with the mean trajectory retraced using univariate spline interpolation. To visualize an intermediate stage of interpolation, we used a smoothing parameter lower than optimal. With respect to the supervised training and assignment process, an example of performance on the internal and external validation sets for cluster assignment based on our ensemble model is shown in Table 1. These results were obtained by **maxVoting** (**sklearn**) on an ensemble of several classifiers as indicated in the previous section. RF bagging ensembles with ensemble averaging obtained accuracies of $65\% \pm 5\%$ for 10-fold cross-validation.

5 Discussion & Outlook

The proposed method can provide both the stratification of patients and the forecast of their mean progression trajectory per group, based on the data available at the first assessment, allowing clinicians to make early decisions on treatment type and cohort assignment for each patient. The method involves unsupervised trajectory clustering and supervised classification, associating trajectory groups

Table 1. Performance on internal and external validation datasets

Group	External Validation				Internal Validation			
	Precision	Recall	f1-score	support	Precision	Recall	f1-score	support
1	0.71	0.73	0.72	74	0.68	0.82	0.74	62
2	0.59	0.64	0.61	90	0.54	0.61	0.57	84
3	0.6	0.55	0.58	100	0.67	0.67	0.67	104
4	0.74	0.71	0.73	52	0.77	0.51	0.62	72
accuracy			0.65	316			0.65	322
macro avg	0.66	0.66	0.66	316	0.67	0.65	0.65	322
weighted avg	0.65	0.65	0.65	316	0.66	0.65	0.65	322

to the data available at the first assessment. This approach differs from other pre-clustering methods that use multivariate clustering on static or longitudinal data and use classifiers to predict time-to-event outcomes within 3-6 months.

As the association between clinical features and the ALSFRS-R scores may be weak, this can lead to a low performance of the classifiers. As such we will continue the analysis with an investigation of methods and the confidence associated with individual assignments. The results presented are still preliminary but do offer promise for systematic cohort identification and assignment. Future work will explore the nature of misclassified cases and means to improve prediction performance. Clinical interpretability of clusters will also be assessed, although the ALSFRS-R trajectory as a global functional scores evolution, may not be directly linked to a specific clinical factor, but to a combined effect.

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